

STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE CYLINDERS UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT:

In general, laminated cylindrical shells manufactured by filament-winding show the coupling effects and behave differently from homogeneous orthotropic ones.

In the first part, stress distributions in the laminated cylindrical shells due to such coupling effects are examined by use of the Donnell equation under the boundary conditions of clamped edges. The typical conclusions which can be summarized from the present analysis are:

- (1) Circumferential displacement occurs near the edges in the antisymmetric angle-ply laminates.
- (2) Twisting moment occurs near the edges in the symmetric angle-ply laminates.
- (3) Bending moments occur in the central part of cylinder far away from the both edges in the antisymmetric cross-ply laminates.

These coupling effects decrease rapidly and the mechanical behaviors approach those of homogeneous orthotropic laminates as the number of layers increases.

Secondly, the distributions of interlaminar shear and normal stresses near the edges under high lateral shear force, and the effects of stacking sequence and thickness ratio of laminates on them are analysed by using the finite element method because of low interlaminar shear strength and stiffness in laminates. It is concluded that the interlaminar shear stresses decrease rapidly away from the clamped edges, but are considerably higher near the edges, especially for the case of large thickness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The pressure vessels manufactured by filament-winding technique have been applied to the rocket chamber [1] [2] [3]. Such laminated shells under internal pressure behave differently from homogeneous orthotropic shells due to the coupling effect, except for the case of symmetric cross-ply laminates. For example, especially for the shell composed of a small number of laminae, the circumferential displacement occurs generally near the clamped edges. This is due to the coupling effect which results in showing the singular stress distributions across laminates. In addition, the transverse shear stresses become significant in the vicinity of the clamped edge of laminated cylinders. Therefore, the effect of such transverse shear deformation must be considered because of low interlaminar shear strength and shear stiffness [4].

Prior to entering into the discussion of practical filament-wound pressure vessels, a laminated cylindrical shell clamped at both edges under internal pressure is considered in the present paper. First, the coupling effect is studied by use of the Donnell equation taking account of the coupling terms. Secondly, the transverse stress distributions through the thickness are analyzed by use of the finite element method. Finally, the effects of thickness and lamination angle on interlaminar shear stresses are discussed.

2. ANALYSES FOR LAMINATED CYLINDRICAL SHELLS UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE

2.1 Analysis by Donnell Equation

The coordinates and the configuration notations used for cylindrical shell are illustrated in Fig.1. The laminates consist of n homogeneous orthotropic laminae as shown in Fig.2 and the fiber in the kth lamina is oriented at θ_k degree to the cylinder axis (x-axis) as shown in Fig.3.

The plane stress-strain relations of the kth lamina are written in terms of principal cylinder coordinates as follows.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(k)} = [T^{(k)}][Q^{(k)}][T^{(k)}]^T \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(k)} = [\bar{Q}^{(k)}] \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}^{(k)} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Cylindrical shell geometry and shell coordinate system.

Fig. 2. Laminate cross-section.

Fig. 3. Directions of fibers and principal axes.

where $[Q]$ is the orthotropic stiffness matrix referred to the principal material coordinates and $[T]$ is the transformation matrix, then $[\bar{Q}]$ is the transformed stiffness matrix referred to the shell coordinate. These are given as follows.

$$[Q^{(k)}] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}^{(k)} & Q_{12}^{(k)} & 0 \\ Q_{12}^{(k)} & Q_{22}^{(k)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad [T^{(k)}] = \begin{bmatrix} l^2 & m^2 & 2lm \\ m^2 & l^2 & -2lm \\ -lm & lm & l^2 - m^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= E_L / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{12} = \nu_L E_T / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{22} = E_T / (1 - \nu_L \nu_T), \quad Q_{66} = G_{LT} \\ l &= \cos \theta_k, \quad m = \sin \theta_k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where E, ν and G denote Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and Shear rigidity, respectively, and the subscripts L and T refer to the longitudinal and transverse directions of fibers.

The constitutive equations for laminated cylindrical shells are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^0 \\ K \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \{N\} & ; \text{force resultants} = [N_x, N_y, N_{xy}]^T, \\ \{M\} & ; \text{moment resultants} = [M_x, M_y, M_{xy}]^T, \\ \{\epsilon^0\} & ; \text{in-plane strains} = [\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \tau_{xy}]^T, \\ \{K\} & ; \text{curvatures} = [\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}]^T \\ A_{ij} & ; \text{extensional stiffnesses} = \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} (h_{k+1} - h_k), \\ B_{ij} & ; \text{coupling stiffnesses} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} (h_{k+1}^2 - h_k^2), \\ D_{ij} & ; \text{bending stiffnesses} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)} (h_{k+1}^3 - h_k^3), \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

In laminated cylindrical shells subjected to internal pressure, $\partial u / \partial y = \partial v / \partial y = \partial w / \partial y$ are usually equal to zero due to axi-symmetry. However, the circumferential displacement, v , occurs differently from the homogeneous orthotropic shells. The displacement components u, v, w are given by functions of axial coordinate x only. Accordingly, the governing equilibrium equations are given in terms of non-dimensional variables as follows [5] [6].

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{A}_{11} \bar{u}_{, \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{16} \bar{v}_{, \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{12} \bar{w}_{, \xi} - \bar{B}_{11} \bar{w}_{, \xi \xi \xi} &= 0, \\ \bar{A}_{16} \bar{u}_{, \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{66} \bar{v}_{, \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{26} \bar{w}_{, \xi} - \bar{B}_{16} \bar{w}_{, \xi \xi \xi} &= 0, \\ \bar{A}_{12} \bar{u}_{, \xi} - \bar{B}_{11} \bar{u}_{, \xi \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{26} \bar{v}_{, \xi} - \bar{B}_{16} \bar{v}_{, \xi \xi \xi} + \bar{D}_{11} \bar{w}_{, \xi \xi \xi \xi} - 2 \bar{B}_{12} \bar{w}_{, \xi \xi} + \bar{A}_{22} \bar{w} &= \bar{p} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \xi &= x/r, \quad \bar{u}, \bar{v}, \bar{w} = u/r, v/r, w/r, \quad \bar{p} = \frac{pr}{Q_{11}h} \\ (\bar{A}_{ij}, \bar{B}_{ij}, \bar{D}_{ij}) &= \frac{1}{Q_{11}h} \left(A_{ij}, \frac{1}{r} B_{ij}, \frac{1}{r^2} D_{ij} \right) \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

They are solved by imposing the following displacement and stress boundary conditions, that is, all the displacements are clamped at one end, but in-plane displacements are permitted at another end of $x = \ell$.

$$\xi=0: \bar{w}=\bar{w}_{,\xi}=\bar{u}=\bar{v}=0 \quad \xi=\ell/r: \bar{w}=\bar{w}_{,\xi}=0, \quad N_x=pr/2, \quad N_{xy}=0 \quad (8)$$

The solutions of Eqs.(6) for u, v and w are given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{u} \\ \bar{v} \end{array} \right\} = - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{11} & \bar{A}_{16} \\ \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{A}_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{12} - \bar{B}_{11} \\ \bar{A}_{26} - \bar{B}_{16} \end{bmatrix} [J] \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C_5 \\ C_7 \\ C_9 \end{bmatrix} \xi + \begin{bmatrix} C_8 \\ C_9 \end{bmatrix} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{w} \\ \bar{w}_{,\xi\xi} \end{array} \right\} = [K] \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} C_6 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $[J]$ and $[K]$ are 2×4 matrices and the elements are given by the following equations.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} J_{11} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\mu_0 \ell' + \nu_0 m') / \gamma, & J_{12} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\mu_0 m' - \nu_0 \ell') / \gamma, & J_{13} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\nu_0 m' - \mu_0 \ell') / \gamma, \\ J_{14} &= -e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\mu_0 m' + \nu_0 \ell') / \gamma, & J_{21} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\mu_0 \ell' - \nu_0 m'), & J_{22} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\nu_0 \ell' + \mu_0 m') \\ J_{23} &= -e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\mu_0 \ell' + \nu_0 m'), & J_{24} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\nu_0 \ell' - \mu_0 m') \\ K_{11} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} \ell', & K_{12} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} m', & K_{13} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} \ell', & K_{14} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} m', & K_{21} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\alpha \ell' - \beta m'), \\ K_{22} &= e^{\mu_0 \ell} (\beta \ell' + \alpha m'), & K_{23} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\alpha \ell' + \beta m'), & K_{24} &= e^{-\mu_0 \ell} (\alpha m' - \beta \ell') \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_0 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{|\bar{A}|/|\bar{D}_1|} - |\bar{B}_1|/|\bar{D}_1|}, & \nu_0 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{|\bar{A}|/|\bar{D}_1|} + |\bar{B}_1|/|\bar{D}_1|} \\ |\bar{A}| &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{11} & \bar{A}_{12} & \bar{A}_{16} \\ \bar{A}_{12} & \bar{A}_{22} & \bar{A}_{26} \\ \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{A}_{26} & \bar{A}_{66} \end{bmatrix}, & |\bar{B}_1| &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{11} & \bar{A}_{12} & \bar{A}_{16} \\ \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{A}_{26} & \bar{A}_{66} \\ \bar{B}_{11} & \bar{B}_{12} & \bar{B}_{16} \end{bmatrix}, & |\bar{D}_1| &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{11} & \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{B}_{11} \\ \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{A}_{66} & \bar{B}_{16} \\ \bar{B}_{11} & \bar{B}_{16} & \bar{D}_{11} \end{bmatrix} \\ \alpha &= \mu_0^2 - \nu_0^2, \quad \beta = 2\mu_0\nu_0, \quad \gamma = \mu_0^2 + \nu_0^2 & \ell' &= \cos \nu_0 \xi, \quad m' = \sin \nu_0 \xi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The integral constants C_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, 9$) are given by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \end{Bmatrix} &= [\bar{A}]^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{p}/2 \\ \bar{p} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, & \begin{Bmatrix} C_8 \\ C_9 \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{11} & \bar{A}_{16} \\ \bar{A}_{16} & \bar{A}_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}_{12} - \bar{B}_{11} \\ \bar{A}_{26} - \bar{B}_{16} \end{bmatrix} [J]_{\xi=0} \begin{Bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{Bmatrix} \\ C_1/C_6 &= (e^{-\mu_0^*} - \cos \nu_0^* - \delta \sin \nu_0^*) / \Omega, & C_2/C_6 &= (-\delta e^{-\mu_0^*} + \delta \cos \nu_0^* - \sin \nu_0^*) / \Omega \\ C_3/C_6 &= (-e^{\mu_0^*} + \delta \cos \nu_0^* - \sin \nu_0^*) / \Omega, & C_4/C_6 &= (-\delta e^{\mu_0^*} + \delta \cos \nu_0^* + \sin \nu_0^*) / \Omega \\ \Omega &= 2(\text{sh } \mu_0^* + \delta \sin \nu_0^*) \\ \mu_0^* &= \mu_0 \ell / r, \quad \nu_0^* = \nu_0 \ell / r, \quad \delta = \mu_0 / \nu_0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

When the more exact Flügge theory [7] for a cylindrical shell is used with the following boundary condition in place of $N_{xy}=0$ in Eq.(8),

$$N_{xy} + M_{xy}/r = 0 \quad (13)$$

the solution can be given by the same expression as Eq.(9) with the following substitution.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{A}_{11} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{11} + \bar{B}_{11}, \quad \bar{A}_{12} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{12}, \quad \bar{A}_{22} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{22} - \bar{B}_{22} + \bar{D}_{22}, \quad \bar{A}_{16} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{16} + 2\bar{B}_{16} + \bar{D}_{16}, \quad \bar{A}_{26} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{26} + \bar{B}_{26}, \\ \bar{A}_{66} \rightarrow \bar{A}_{66} + 3\bar{B}_{66} + 3\bar{D}_{66}, \quad \bar{B}_{11} \rightarrow \bar{B}_{11} + \bar{D}_{11}, \quad \bar{B}_{16} \rightarrow \bar{B}_{16} + 2\bar{D}_{16}, \quad \bar{B}_{12} \rightarrow \bar{B}_{12}, \quad \bar{D}_{11} \rightarrow \bar{D}_{11} \end{aligned} \right\} (14)$$

2.2 Analysis for Transverse Stresses by Finite Element Method

It is necessary to know the distributions of transverse stresses near the clamped edges under high transverse shear force, because the interlaminar shear strength is low in laminates. The transverse stress distributions which can not be obtained by Donnell equation, are analysed by the finite element method with mesh division as shown in Fig.4. It is assumed that the laminae remain bonded together and the no slippage occurs and so the displacements between laminae are continuous.

(1) Strain-Displacement Relations

$$\epsilon_x = u_{,x}, \quad \epsilon_y = w/(r+z), \quad \epsilon_z = w_{,z}, \quad \gamma_{xy} = v_{,x}, \quad \gamma_{yz} = v_{,z} - v/(r+z), \quad \gamma_{zx} = w_{,x} + u_{,z} \quad (15)$$

(2) Strain-Nodal Displacement Relations

The displacements u, v and w are expressed by linear functions of x and z . The strain-nodal displacement relations are expressed by

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B]\{\delta\}^e \quad (16)$$

where $\{\delta\}^e$ is the nodal displacement vector of a triangular element and $[B]$ is the matrix which shows the strain-nodal displacement relations.

(3) Stress-Strain Relations

Each layer in laminates being transversely isotropic, the stress-strain relations for each triangular element can be expressed similarly to Eq.(1) by referring to the shell coordinates.

$$\{\sigma\} = [T][Q][T]^T \{\epsilon\} = [D]\{\epsilon\} \quad (17)$$

where

$$\{\sigma\} = [\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{zx}]^T \quad \{\epsilon\} = [\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_z, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{yz}, \gamma_{zx}]^T$$

$[Q]$ is the three-dimensional stiffness matrix referred to the principal material coordinates for transversely isotropic material, and $[T]$ is the transformation matrix. The symmetrical matrix elements Q_{ij} ($i, j=1, 2, \dots, 6$) can be expressed as follows.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= (1 - \nu_{TT})E_L / (1 - \nu_{TT} - 2\nu_L\nu_T), & Q_{12} &= \nu_L E_T / (1 - \nu_{TT} - 2\nu_L\nu_T), & Q_{13} &= Q_{12} \\ Q_{22} &= (1 - \nu_L\nu_T)E_T / (1 - \nu_{TT} - 2\nu_L\nu_T)(1 + \nu_{TT}), \end{aligned} \right\} (18)$$

Fig. 4. Mesh division used in finite element method.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_{23} &= (\nu_L \nu_T + \nu_{TT}) E_T / (1 - \nu_{TT} - 2\nu_L \nu_T) (1 + \nu_{TT}), \\
 Q_{33} &= Q_{22}, \quad Q_{44} = G_{TT}, \quad Q_{55} = Q_{66} = G_{LT}, \\
 Q_{14} &= Q_{15} = Q_{16} = 0, \quad Q_{24} = Q_{25} = Q_{26} = 0, \quad Q_{34} = Q_{35} = Q_{36} = 0, \quad Q_{45} = Q_{46} = Q_{56} = 0
 \end{aligned}
 \quad \left. \vphantom{\begin{aligned} Q_{23} \\ Q_{33} \\ Q_{14} \end{aligned}} \right\}$$

where G_{TT} and ν_{TT} are shear rigidity and Poisson's ratio, respectively, in the transverse cross-section to fibers. The following relations hold between these elastic constants.

$$\nu_L / E_L = \nu_T / E_T, \quad G_{TT} = E_T / 2(1 + \nu_{TT}) \quad (19)$$

(4) Stiffness Matrix for A Triangular Element, $[K]^e$

$$[K]^e = 2\pi \int_A [B]^T [D] [B] (r+z) dz dx \quad (20)$$

where $[B]$ is functions of x and z and can be calculated with the numerical integral technique by Gauss.

(5) Mesh Division and Boundary Conditions

The shell is divided into elements in both x and z directions with a distance far enough from one edge until the bending moments diminish. The number of division through the thickness is 16 or 32.

The boundary conditions at one clamped edge are $u=v=0$ and $w=0$ or w is constrained to zero only at the mid-plane. At another edge, the nodal forces are applied so as to satisfy the condition of $N_x = pr/2$ with $v=0$.

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

The elastic constants of unidirectional carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy composites with fiber volume content $V_f = 60\%$ used for numerical examples are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_L &= 137 \text{ GPa} (13940 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2), \quad E_T = 8.17 \text{ GPa} (833 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2), \quad G_{LT} = 4.75 \text{ GPa} (484 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2), \\
 \nu_L &= 0.316, \quad \nu_{TT} = 0.48 (G_{TT} = 2.76 \text{ GPa} (281 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2)) \\
 r &= 100 \text{ mm}, \quad pr/h = 0.98 \text{ GPa} (10 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2)
 \end{aligned}
 \quad (21)$$

These values can be obtained by explicit algebraic equations when the constituent materials and V_f are specified, and they are confirmed by experiments [8] [9]. The radius of cylinder r is taken as 100mm in the following numerical calculation.

3.1 Stiffnesses of Laminates

In general laminates, the coupling terms such as

$$A_{16}, A_{26}, D_{16}, D_{26}, B_{ij} (i, j = 1, 2, 6)$$

appear in Eq.(4) differently from the homogeneous orthotropic materials. The effects of the stacking sequence and the number of layers, n , on the coupling terms are discussed for the following typical laminates.

3.1.1 Angle-ply Laminates

In the angle-ply laminates consisting of $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ laminae, the extensional stiffnesses A_{11} , A_{22} , A_{12} and A_{66} are constant independently of n as shown in Fig.5. However, the extension-twisting (shear-bending) coupling stiffnesses B_{16} , B_{26} appear in antisymmetric angle-ply laminates as shown in Fig.6. The extension-shear coupling stiffnesses A_{16} , A_{26} and the bending-twisting coupling stiffnesses D_{16} , D_{26} appear in symmetric angle-ply laminates as shown in Fig.7. These stiffnesses are shown in terms of the following normalized values in the above figures.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{A}_{16}^* &= (-1)^{(n-1)/2} A_{16}/Q_{11}h, \quad \bar{B}_{16}^* = B_{16}/Q_{11}h^2, \quad \bar{D}_{16}^* = (-1)^{(n-1)/2} D_{16}/(Q_{11}h^3/12), \\ Q_{11} &= E_L/(1-\nu_L\nu_T) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

The values of A_{26} , B_{26} and D_{26} can be obtained by replacing θ° with $(90^\circ-\theta^\circ)$ in those of A_{16} , B_{16} and D_{16} , respectively.

Fig. 5. Variations of in-plane stiffness with lamination angle.

Fig. 6. Variations of coupling stiffness B_{16} with lamination angle in antisymmetric angle-ply laminate.

(a) odd

(b) even

Fig. 7. Variations of coupling stiffnesses A_{16} and D_{16} with lamination angle and number of layers in symmetric angle-ply laminate.

The coupling stiffnesses are functions of the number of layers, n , as described in the following equations.

$$A_{16}, B_{16} \propto \frac{1}{n}, D_{16} \propto \left(\frac{1}{n} - \frac{2}{3n^3} \right) \quad (23)$$

3.1.2 Cross-ply Laminates

In the cross-ply laminates consisting of the 0° and 90° laminae, $A_{16}=A_{26}=0$ and $D_{16}=D_{26}=0$. No coupling term appears in symmetric laminates, but the coupling terms $B_{11}=-B_{22}$ appear in antisymmetric laminates as shown in Fig.8. It comes from the difference in locations between the middle and neutral planes.

Fig. 8. Variation of coupling stiffness B_{11} with number of layers in antisymmetric cross-ply laminate.

3.2 Laminated Cylindrical Shells with Clamped Edges

(Solution by Donnell Equation)

3.2.1 Angle-ply Laminated Cylindrical Shells

In the angle-ply laminates consisting of $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ laminae with equal thickness, the resultant force N and the resultant moment M can be obtained by substituting the strains derived from Eq.(9) into Eq.(4). The axial bending moment at the clamped edge, $(M_x)_0$, and the axial length ξ_0 away from the edge where M_x decreases to 1% of $(M_x)_0$ are shown in the following equations.

$$(M_x)_0 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{A}_{12}}{2\bar{A}_{11}} \right) \sqrt{\frac{\bar{D}_{11} - \bar{B}_{16}^2 / \bar{A}_{66}}{\bar{D}_{22} - \bar{D}_{12}^2 / \bar{D}_{11}}} p r \quad (24)$$

$$\xi_0 = 3.8 \sqrt{\frac{h}{r}} \sqrt[4]{\frac{\bar{D}_{11} - \bar{B}_{16}^2 / \bar{A}_{66}}{\bar{D}_{22} - \bar{D}_{12}^2 / \bar{D}_{11}}} \quad (25)$$

(1) Distributions of Axial Resultant Forces and Moments

The resultant forces and moments in symmetric and antisymmetric laminates are compared with each other in Fig.9 for the case of $\theta=45^\circ$. Little difference can be seen in both curves for resultant forces, but much difference can be seen for resultant moments. Especially, the distributions of twisting moment M_{xy} are non-zero for both laminates and are quite different, although M_{xy} is zero in the homogeneous orthotropic cylindrical shells. In the symmetric laminates, M_{xy} becomes maximum at the clamped edge due to the effect of coupling stiffness D_{16} and decreases rapidly away from the edge. On the contrary, it should be noted that in the antisymmetric laminates, M_{xy} becomes maximum at the central part of cylinder far away from the edges.

The bending moments M_x and M_y in the symmetric laminates are equal to those in homogeneous orthotropic ones, but those in the antisymmetric laminates are considerably lower due to the effect of coupling stiffness B_{16} . The higher bending moments are confined only in the vicinity of the clamped edges.

Fig. 9. Distributions of resultant forces and moments near the edge in angle-ply laminate.

Fig. 10. Maximum bending moment at the edge versus lamination angle in angle-ply laminates.

Fig. 11. Variations of twisting moments with lamination angle in angle-ply laminate.

(2) Relationship between Maximum Moment at Clamped Edge and Laminated Angle

The values of maximum bending moments $(M_x)_0$ and $(M_y)_0$ at the clamped edges depend considerably on the lamination angle θ as shown in Fig.10, which results from the remarkable changes of bending stiffnesses. It can be seen that the bending moments in antisymmetric laminates become lower due to the coupling term B_{16} and approach to those for homogeneous shells as the number of layers increases, for example, two to four.

The twisting moment M_{xy} at the clamped edges in symmetric and antisymmetric laminates and those at the central part of cylinder far away from the edges in antisymmetric laminates are shown against the lamination angle θ in Fig.11. $(M_{xy})_0$ in symmetric laminates become maximum when θ is nearly equal to 30° . While, $M_{xy,max}$

Fig. 12. Distributions of resultant forces and moments near the edge in cross-ply laminates.

in antisymmetric laminates takes a maximum value when θ is nearly equal to 45° , and its magnitude decreases by half as the number of layers increases from two to four.

3.2.2 Cross-ply Laminated Cylindrical Shells

The distributions of resultant forces N_x , N_y and bending moments M_x , M_y in cross-ply laminated cylindrical shells are shown in Fig.12. The maximum bending moments (M_x)₀ at the clamped edge depend on the stacking sequence because of large difference of bending stiffnesses.

In antisymmetric laminates, the coupling terms $B_{11} = -B_{22}$ appear because the middle surface does not coincide with the neutral surface. Accordingly, the axial bending moment M_x about the middle surface occurs even in the central part of cylinder far away from the clamped edges.

3.3 Solutions by F.E.M. and Comparison with those by Donnell Equation

The displacements at the middle surface in the two-layered antisymmetric angle-ply laminated cylinder $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ obtained by F.E.M. and Donnell equation are compared in Fig.13. Since the circumferential displacement v occurs near the edges, the plane stresses σ_x and σ_y become discontinuous through the laminae as shown in Fig.14. Even in symmetric angle-ply laminates as shown in the middle of Fig.14 $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ]$, the circumferential displacement v appears in the solutions obtained by F.E.M. or Flügge equation. However it is so small for the case of thin shell with $h/r=1/100$ that the plane stresses obtained by F.E.M. are almost the same as those by the Donnell equation, for which $v=0$, as seen in Figs.13 and 14.

Fig. 13. Distributions of displacement components in the middle surface near the edge in angle-ply $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ laminate.

Fig. 14. Comparison of plane stress distributions through the thickness obtained by FEM and Donnell equation.

3.4 Transverse Stresses Obtained by F.E.M.

The distributions of transverse shear stresses τ_{zx} , τ_{yz} and transverse normal stress σ_z near the clamped edge are shown in Fig.15 for the case of two-layered angle-ply $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ cylindrical shell, as an example.

τ_{zx} is highest among all these transverse stresses and the distributions of τ_{zx} through the thickness are not always parabolic. In addition, it can be seen that the transverse shear stresses decrease rapidly away from the clamped edges.

Fig. 15. Transverse stress distributions near the edge through the thickness in $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ laminate.

Fig. 16. Distributions of interlaminar shear stress in the middle surface as a parameter of lamination angle.

The axial distributions of interlaminar shear stress τ_{zx} in the middle surface are shown in Fig.16 as a parameter of lamination angle, θ . τ_{zx} in the middle surface becomes higher as θ decreases. This comes from the fact that the derivative of axial bending moment, dM_x/dx , that is, the transverse shear force, Q_x , becomes higher as θ decreases.

The axial distributions of interlaminar shear stress τ_{zx} in the middle surface are shown in Fig.17 as a parameter of shell thickness ratio h/r for the case of two-layered antisymmetric angle-ply $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ cylindrical shell, as an example. It is found that τ_{zx} becomes higher as the shell becomes thicker.

In the above numerical examples, the boundary conditions at one edge are $u=v=w=0$. The numerical results under the boundary conditions of $u=v=0$ and $w_{center}=0$ are compared with the former results in Fig.18. The effect of such boundary conditions for w on the τ_{zx} distribution is limited to the region near the edge. The case where w is constrained only in the middle surface gives higher values than the case of $w=0$ throughout the thickness.

The distributions of τ_{zx} in the middle surface in the symmetric cross-ply laminates are shown in Fig.19 as a parameter of thickness ratio. Similarly to angle-ply laminates, the interlaminar shear stress τ_{zx} increases with an increase of

Fig. 17. Distributions of interlaminar shear stress in the middle surface as a parameter of thickness ratio.

Fig. 18. Variation of distribution of interlaminar shear stress in the middle surface with boundary conditions.

thickness ratio and occurs only in the limited region near the clamped edge.

Next, the stress distributions referring to the fiber direction through the thickness near the clamped edge ($x/h=1.0$) for the two kinds of thickness ratios are shown in Fig.20, in symmetric angle-ply laminates $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ]$, as an example. These stresses are shown by the values normalized by the following fundamental failure strengths of unidirectional composites. That is,

- | | | |
|----------|---|-----------------------------------|
| F_L | ; tensile strength in the fiber direction | =1470MPa(150Kg/mm ²), |
| F_L' | ; compressive strength in the fiber direction | =981MPa(100Kg/mm ²), |
| F_T | ; tensile strength normal to fibers | =39.2MPa(4.0Kg/mm ²), |
| F_T' | ; compressive strength normal to fibers | =118MPa(12Kg/mm ²), |
| F_{LT} | ; shearing strength along fibers | =78.5MPa(8.0Kg/mm ²), |
| F_{TT} | ; shearing strength in the transverse section to fibers | =58.9MPa(6.0Kg/mm ²) |

As seen from Fig.20, $\bar{\sigma}_T$ is highest among these normalized stresses because of low value of F_T . $\bar{\tau}_{Lz}$ and $\bar{\tau}_{Tz}$ are so lower as compared with $\bar{\sigma}_T$ and $\bar{\tau}_{LT}$ that they can be neglected even near the clamped edges where the transverse shear stresses are high, especially in thin shells. However, $\bar{\tau}_{Tz}$ increases to about one half of $\bar{\sigma}_T$ which is highest for the case of thick shells such as $h/r=5/100$.

Fig. 19. Variations of interlaminar shear stress in the middle surface in cross-ply laminate with thickness ratio.

Fig.20. Distributions of stresses referring to the fiber direction through the thickness near the clamped edges in symmetric angle-ply laminate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the first part, the coupling effects in laminated cylindrical shells under internal pressure are analysed by use of the Donnell equation. The coupling effects become significant as the number of layers decrease, and the mechanical behaviors become different from those of homogeneous laminates.

- (1) In the antisymmetric angle-ply laminates, the circumferential displacement occurs near the clamped edges and hence in-plane stresses become discontinuous across laminae. Twisting moment becomes highest in the central portion of cylinder far away from the both ends.
- (2) In the symmetric angle-ply laminates, twisting moments occur near the edges.
- (3) In the antisymmetric cross-ply laminates, bending moments occur because of the different locations of the neutral and middle surfaces.
- (4) The Donnell theory is sufficient in accuracy for analysing thin laminated cylindrical shells where the transverse shear deformation can be neglected.

In the second part, the distributions of transverse and in-plane stresses are analysed by using the finite element method. The effects of stacking sequence and thickness ratio of laminates on the stress distributions are discussed.

- (5) The axial interlaminar shear stress decreases rapidly away from the clamped edges, but is considerably high near the edges especially in the case of large thickness.
- (6) The distribution of axial interlaminar shear stress through the thickness is not generally parabolic.

It can be concluded that the coupling effects and the transverse shear deformation should be taken into consideration in the laminated cylindrical shells under internal pressure especially with a small number of layers and with large thickness.

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